

Bridging the gap between smart cities and sustainability: Current practices and future trends[☆]

Qinhuan Gu^{a,*}, Michael C.P. Sing^b, Marcus Jefferies^a, Sittimont Kanjanabootra^a

^a School of Built Environment, University of Newcastle, Callaghan, NSW 2308, Australia

^b Department of Building and Real Estate, the Hong Kong Polytechnic University, Hong Kong, China

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ABSTRACT

As smart cities expand rapidly due to urbanization, economic growth, and political support, concerns around sustainability have emerged. There is a lack of supporting frameworks that describe the interactions and behaviors of key variables facilitating the sustainability of smart cities. This study aims to formulate a conceptual framework linking smart cities and sustainability through a systematic literature review. A review was conducted which yielded extensive insights into sustainability in smart cities. Out of the 2596 articles examined, 82 focus on smart cities and sustainability. A bibliometric analysis was performed to identify the authorship and affiliation of selected publications, followed by a content analysis offering a detailed assessment of the studies. First, the literature review revealed a robust connection between smart cities and sustainability, as illustrated through a network visualization diagram. Second, the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) theory was employed to elucidate crucial elements of smart cities and their relationships with sustainability. Finally, a conceptual framework was formulated to explain the principal factors promoting the sustainability of smart cities. The findings have significant managerial and strategic implications for the advancement of smart cities and suggest potential areas for further research in exploring sustainability within smart cities.

1. Introduction

Cities are major sites of human progress and civilization and growth in urbanization has caused economic and environmental impacts on cities (Liu et al., 2021). Given continuous city development and the advent of the information era, urban types are changing and evolving. As the rhythm of city life accelerated and social mobility increases, diverse urban challenges like traffic congestion, environmental degradation, and urban poverty continue to emerge and grow (Bibri, 2021). The emergence of these problems has popularized the execution of smart city strategies by municipal governments (Allam and Newman, 2018). A smart city is one that uses technology and data to improve the quality of life of its citizens and enhance the efficiency of urban services such as transportation, energy, and public security (Goyal et al., 2020). Globally, the number of smart cities is expected to expand continually (Kong et al., 2022; Vanli, 2024).

Sustainability is an inexorable concern that cannot be neglected in any urban context, particularly given the significant criticisms it has

faced (Bibri, 2019). Sustainability is the quality of not depleting or exhausting natural resources in order to avoid exhausting resources for future generations (Kuhlman and Farrington, 2010). Moldan et al. (2012) also define sustainability as the ability to continue to maintain or facilitate a level of activity or life within a context or system over a long period without depleting natural resources or causing serious ecological damage.

Smart cities are inherently connected with sustainability (Bibri, 2021). Smart cities can pioneer advanced urban planning paradigms and improve quality and performance of urban services with the integration of technology. Furthermore, sustainability can support the development of smart cities along long time horizons and according to innovative ideas (Aelenei et al., 2016). As an illustration, smart city technologies can be implemented to substantially decrease the energy consumption of the building infrastructure (Bhati et al., 2017), to encourage citizens to switch transportation modes (Aletà et al., 2017), and to augment local waste-management systems (Evans et al., 2019). Moreover, building design and construction can make a significant contribution to the

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* Corresponding author at: School of Built Environment, University of Newcastle, Callaghan, NSW 2308, Australia.

E-mail addresses: c3371092@uon.edu.au (Q. Gu), michael.sing@polyu.edu.hk (M.C.P. Sing), marcus.jefferies@newcastle.edu.au (M. Jefferies), sittimont.kanjanabootra@newcastle.edu.au (S. Kanjanabootra).

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sustainability of smart cities (Ahvenniemi et al., 2017), because buildings can lower their carbon emissions and enhance the comprehensive sustainability of the city through the adoption of energy-saving materials and sustainable approaches. Therefore, sustainability is a core attribute of smart cities.

While there are several seminal studies such as those Bibri and Krogstie (2017) and Trindade et al. (2017) have explored the connections between smart cities and sustainability, the scope of existing research often remains limited to conceptual mappings of assessment frameworks or specific technological alignment. For instance, Ahvenniemi et al. (2017) systematically compared eight sustainable city assessment frameworks with eight smart city assessment frameworks, revealing overlaps and gaps in how these frameworks address environmental, economic, and social dimensions. Similarly, Margherita et al. (2023) employed a structural topic modelling approach to examine a corpus of smart city proposals from Belgian municipalities, identifying nine categories of smart urban technologies that potentially influence urban sustainability across the triple bottom line. However, what remains underexplored in these studies is the integration of smart city and sustainability factors into a comprehensive and dynamic framework that captures the evolving interplay among governance, stakeholder engagement, and managerial strategy.

Building on this foundation, the present study aims to extend previous research by systematically integrating the essential elements of smart cities and sustainability into a comprehensive and actionable framework. Initially, information was gathered systematically to obtain a comprehensive understanding of sustainability in smart cities. Next, using a bibliometric analysis, the co-occurrence of keywords and co-citation network analysis were identified to capture connections and interactions of the key variables influencing sustainability in smart cities. Next, the key variables identified from bibliometric analysis, in line with the Triple Bottom Line (TBL) theory, were evaluated through content analysis. Finally, a conceptual framework was posted to capture the association among sustainability and smart cities. Using this proposed conceptual framework within the study, this research provides an integrative understanding of key variables pertinent to sustainability in smart cities.

2. Literature review

2.1. The development of a smart city

Cities serve as the primary spatial carriers of human development (Liu et al. (2021) and are sources of power for the advancement of humanity and civilization (Morgan, 2019). Since the industrial revolution, the pace of urbanization has accelerated worldwide, such that urbanization is currently considered the dominant trend in social development (Silva et al., 2018). Although the potential benefits resulting from urbanization are clear (including the expanding city scale, rapid economic development, accelerated pace of lifestyle, and increased social mobility) several urban concerns, such as traffic congestion, environmental pollution, and difficulties in urban governance (Bakıcı et al., 2013) have emerged simultaneously. These problems considerably impede the sustainable growth of cities and are among the most intractable challenges facing contemporary societies (Dincă et al., 2022). Given continuous progress in social development and the advent of the information era, cities are transforming and evolving (Zhou et al., 2021). These changes are reflected in the shifting priorities and objectives that urban administrators have demanded of urban governance over time.

Beginning with digital cities and intelligent cities (Wilkinson, 1991), cities have been shaped by city administrators with particular focus on diverse concerns from the 21st century onwards, such as concerns clustered loosely around notions of Eco city and Knowledge city (Yigitcanlar et al., 2008). Consequently, policymakers and facilitators exhibit increased interest within the ecological, economic, and societal

perspectives of urban governance, spurring the advancement of ecologically sustainable smart cities (Kashef et al., 2021).

2.2. The concept of a smart city

According to Ritchie and Roser (2018), two-thirds of the world's population will be living in cities by 2050, indicating accelerating levels of global urbanization. 750 cities worldwide will contribute approximately US\$80 trillion to the world economy by 2030, accounting for 61% of the world's total GDP (Daptardar and Gore, 2019). However, opportunities and problems usually coexist as population expansion will exacerbate various problems that cities have long encountered, such as environmental pollution (Seuwou et al., 2020), excessive energy consumption, and traffic congestion (Wang and Debbage, 2021). To counteract these obstacles and achieve long-term sustainable development, stakeholders have become the first choice to improve scientific decision-making and urban governance.

Smart cities could facilitate the expansion of the digital economy and be foundational in addressing various urban challenges (Evans et al., 2019). The visionary framework of a smart city leverages ICT to amalgamate diverse urban management systems efficiently (Bibri, 2021), thus facilitating information resource sharing and business synergies. Additionally, this approach is favorable for fostering intelligent advancement in urban management and services, enhancing the standard of urban operations and management, optimizing public services in areas like transportation, health systems, and resource allocation. These improvements and smart governance could contribute to elevating the overall quality of life for urban residents and help cities move towards more sustainable development (De Guimarães et al., 2020).

2.2.1. The evolution of a smart city

As smart cities further evolve and upgrade, they have evolved from applying information technology products to the in-depth integration of information technology and urban modernization (Wang et al., 2019). The smart city scheme is believed to have evolved from the application of localized IT tools to the innovative integration of applications in a widely connected environment (Lu et al., 2019). Governmental planners aim to enhance smart cities by improving upon measurable aspects of their administrations such as urban governance, ecological sustainability, public services, and economic growth (Visvizi et al., 2018). Moreover, they aim to continuously promote the modernization of urban governance systems and strengthen governance capacity.

2.2.2. Existing studies on smart city and sustainability

As the most innovative form of a city, the smart city reflects a global trend and is gaining a wide response from society (Appio et al., 2019). The development of smart cities synchronizes urbanization and industrialization to attain an advanced level of integration. Sustainability is a critical element of smart city development, but has been debated in the context of organizational management rather than urban governance.

Researchers have defined sustainable smart cities in various ways. Kashef et al. (2021) defines the sustainability of a smart city as manifested in urban ecosystems such as infrastructure, policies, and controls (Liu et al., 2021). According to Garau and Pavan (2018), a sustainable smart city can be constructed to be adaptive, reliable, scalable, accessible, and flexible. Trindade et al. (2017) propose that the experience of a smart city should be considered when assessing it. This means that an elevated standard of living, environmental friendliness, and livable conditions could be provided within a sustainable smart city. Umar et al. (2020) emphasize that sustainable development and that smart cities should emphasize environmental, economic, and social aspects. Although several reviews have explored the relationship between sustainability and smart cities, these studies have primarily focused on broad conceptual frameworks without providing practical insights into how cities can implement sustainability in a smart urban ecosystems (Aina, 2017; Garau and Pavan, 2018).

Moreover, smart sustainability has received increasing attention in academic literature. It is seen as an important element in aligning urban development with sustainable practices to develop sustainable smart cities. As suggested by Ivars-Baidal et al. (2023) and Perles-Ribes and Baidal (2018), the combination of smart technologies and sustainability can enhance the ecological resilience of cities and promote sustainable tourism as well as resource-efficient urban governance. However, despite the growing emphasis on smart sustainability, research on how to implement the concept in practice remains limited. This research will explore possible ways to fill this gap, building on the conceptual framework presented by these scholars to further investigate how smart cities can transform into truly sustainable urban ecosystems.

2.2.3. Existing dataset and codebase for supporting smart cities

Table 1 provides a summary of existing smart city datasets from the US, UK, Singapore, Hong Kong SAR, and China. And these datasets cover many areas, such as transport, energy, environmental monitoring, and government. They are important to the ability to data-driven decisions and collaborate diverse disciplines.

2.2.4. Development trends and the sustainability gap

While numerous reviews have examined the factors of success among smart cities (Caragliu and Del Bo, 2019), recent trends in smart city development have emphasized advancements in technological innovation, governance models, and citizen-centric approaches (such as Haarstad and Wathne (2019) and Toli and Murtagh (2020)). However, these trends often remain a lack of comprehensive frameworks, failing to offer a holistic integration of smart technologies with the environmental, social, and economic needs of urban ecosystems. This study aims to fill this gap by exploring the integration of environmental, social, and governance principles at the city level, with a specific focus on how smart technologies can support ecological resilience, social equity, and economic vitality in urban settings.

Furthermore, scholars such as Aina (2017) have pointed out the absence of practical tools for urban planners and policymakers to integrate sustainability goals into smart city development. Although existing literature provides some insight into sustainability, this review strives to close this gap through proposing a novel framework that integrates the concept of smart technology with urban sustainability. Unlike previous reviews, which often focus on sustainability at the organizational level, this study addresses city-level sustainability by considering ecological resilience, resource efficiency, and social equity – essential dimensions that long-term sustainable urban transformation.

Hence, this study not only seeks to bridge the identified research gap but also serves as a foundation for future research efforts. While this

Table 1
Summary of Existing Smart City Datasets.

Country/Region	Dataset Name	Domain	Key Features
US	U.S. Open Data Portal	Transportation, Energy	Includes datasets on public transit schedules, traffic patterns, and renewable energy use.
UK	Transport for London (TfL)	Transportation	Implements the transport strategy and to manage transport services.
Singapore	Singapore Government Data	Governance, Mobility	Offers datasets on urban mobility, public services, and environmental monitoring.
Hong Kong SAR	Hong Kong GeoData Store	Environmental Monitoring	Features spatial data for transportation, urban design and building.
China	Beijing & Shanghai Municipal Open Data	Transportation, Energy	Contains transportation data, air pollution levels, and statistics yearbook data.

paper primarily focuses on establishing a theoretical framework, further studies could extend its application to other smart urban contexts and assess its global potential for fostering sustainable urban development.

3. Research methodology

Systematic literature reviews are a well-established method for reviewing and synthesizing literature (Foo et al., 2021) and for this research was conducted to examine the relationship between smart cities and sustainability. A four-stage process was utilized to operationalize the research: (1) literature search and retrieval of eligible studies, (2) bibliometric analysis, (3) content analysis to summarize the findings, and (4) the development of a conceptual framework. The combined approach effectively supplements and enhances the others to unveil the hidden composition, configuration, and patterns of sustainability in smart city research, expose variables influencing sustainability levels, optimize the conceptual framework for sustainability in smart city area and orient future research of sustainability in smart city.

3.1. Stage 1 literature search and retrieval of applicable studies

Using the literature retrieval method suggested by Yaxue (2020), the following steps were conducted in this research and are illustrated in Fig. 1.

(1) Database selection

The literature review was initially performed through the university library search engine, which is indexed in multiple databases and connected to various databases including (i) Scopus, (ii) Web of Science (WOS), (iii) ProQuest, (iv) Springer, and (v) ScienceDirect. Databases such as Scopus and Web of Science index include many IEEE conference papers and journal articles. Therefore, many IEEE publications that focus on smart cities are likely retrieved indirectly through these databases. Each database has unique strengths and coverage and incorporating all of these ensured that the literature review was thorough.

(2) Choosing source types

According to Bibri (2021), the literature includes journal articles, conference papers, books, dissertations, and theses as primary inclusion criteria. Abstracts of key issues and related materials were also included in the search. After deleting duplicate or excessively similar publications, all downloaded publications were manually checked to ensure that the smart city concept was a major part of the papers. Those publications that concerned unrelated topics, such as smart cars and smart watches, were deleted. The literature review was conducted by comparing the research backgrounds and discussing the findings of these articles.

(3) Determining keywords and criteria

Four keywords were utilized to search for related published academic articles, dissertations, and theses. The search line for Node 1 was: ((Full Text Combined: ("smart city")) AND ((Full Text Combined:(sustainability))). The search line for Node 2 was: ((Full Text Combined: ("sustainability")) AND ((Full Text Combined: (urbanization)). The search line for Node 3 was: ((Full Text Combined: ("urbanization")) AND ((Full Text Combined:(urban transformation))). First, 2596 publications (journal articles, conference papers, and dissertations) were identified.

(4) Evaluating sources

According to Allam and Newman (2018), it is sufficient to refer to literature from the past five years to study smart cities. The literature search was performed in May 2023, and a ten-year time span was

Fig. 1. Key Steps in Literature Search and Retrieval of Eligible Studies.

selected to collect representative subsets of data and to eliminate expired data. Finally, 1278 publications (journal articles, conference papers, and dissertations) were included.

After these selected articles had been assessed, the next step was to establish clear and precise selection criteria that could be used to select the ultimate sample of articles. The subsequent criteria were formulated based on research objectives to streamline the retrieved records: the inclusion criteria encompass full-text records available in English from accessible databases and studies related to the theme of smart cities. Conversely, exclusion criteria included articles lacking a clear methodology or failing to offer supporting evidence, references, theoretical foundations, or data analyses to corroborate their findings.

(5) Backward and forward reference searching

After reading the abstract and overall structure of the papers and determining the consistency and accuracy of keyword searches, 248 articles and these were found to be the most relevant to the research theme. Backward and forward reference searches were used to limit the final article sample as suggested by Moynihan et al. (2021). The backward reference search aimed to identify references cited in academic articles and a forward reference search identifies articles cited after publication. This resulted in 82 publications (journal articles,

conference papers and dissertations).

3.2. Stage 2 bibliometric analysis

The literature search was followed by a bibliometric analysis providing quantitative insights into the domain of smart cities through retrospectively analyzing published papers (Wang et al., 2021). This analysis systematically articulated a knowledge map to create a keyword co-occurrence network (Ye et al., 2020) and co-citation network. The keyword co-occurrence network captures the connections and interactions between different areas of scientific knowledge and investigates the relative importance of each component in the network. The analyses were visually presented using VOSviewer which was chosen for its easy-to-use interface for constructing and viewing bibliometric maps. VOSviewer also allows for various display options, and it can highlight a different aspect of the map (Laila, 2021). It features zoom, scroll, and search functions which facilitated detailed views of the map.

3.3. Stage 3 content analysis

This study included a content analysis (aligned with the TBL theory) linking sustainability and smart cities. The frequency and relevance of

specific topics, selected across a range of data, were identified and analyzed to uncover initially imperceptible patterns, trends, and relationships. This method thereby provides a deeper understanding of the field of study or phenomenon using content analysis methods (Dubé and Paré, 2003). In this investigation, a content analysis method was utilized, which aimed to provide a targeted analysis and interpretation of a specific research questions and goals. Content analysis is more focused and specific than full content analysis and the process retains the results of previous research as guidelines.

Based on Elkington (2013) execution, this study utilized the TBL measuring the level of sustainability in smart cities from three aspects: environmental, social, and economic. The content analysis consisted of (1) extraction of identification data (2) review of selected articles analyzing sustainability in smart cities, and (3) selection of environmental, social, and economic variables based on a systematic literature review that affects sustainability.

3.4. Stage 4 development of conceptual framework

A conceptual framework was developed based on a systematic literature review to assess the sustainability of smart cities. This newly

developed framework addresses essential aspects, including environmental, social, economic, technological, administrative, legal, infrastructure, and urban planning factors, along with considerations related to governance and regulation. The newly established framework provides a structural perspective for assessing the project’s sustainability, and it also offers a guideline for future practice of smart city projects and sustainable development and management. These key variables have been widely supported in literature and empirical analysis. For example, Bibri and Krogstie (2017) highlight smart city management as a priority. Socioeconomic factors and social inclusion in economic growth are emphasized in da Silva Tomadon, and do Couto, E. V., de Vries, W. T., and Moretto, Y., (2024). Bifulco et al. (2016) focus on technological progress, safety, and productivity and Ramirez Lopez and Grijalba Castro (2020) identify resilience and stability as key for long-term urban growth.

4. Results and discussions

4.1. Bibliometric analysis of smart city publications

Bibliometric analysis was conducted employing VOSviewer® to

Fig. 2. Co-occurrence of Keywords Visualization.

analyze the co-occurrence of keywords in the selected articles. Based on fractional counting (a method used in bibliometric analysis to evaluate the relevance or significance of elements such as keywords) 175 keywords relating to smart cities and sustainability were identified. As shown in Fig. 2, a network visualization was created consisting of 37 keywords and 19 clusters connected by 634 links.

Fig. 2 shows smart cities and sustainability with thick nodes and lines, highlighting the significant concern for sustainability within smart city initiatives. These initiatives, however, are not only theoretical. For example, the keyword cluster relating to “energy efficiency” demonstrates how specific smart technologies (such as smart grids and IoT-powered monitoring systems) are implemented to reduce energy consumption and improve urban sustainability (Bibri and Krogstie, 2020). Similarly, the keyword “urban mobility” highlights how intelligent transportation systems (such as electric vehicles and real-time traffic management) contribute to reducing carbon emissions and creating more sustainable urban environments (Tariq, 2024).

The co-citation network diagram reveals essential literature in smart city and sustainability studies through its analysis of citation patterns in major publications. Fig. 3 illustrates the frequency of literature citations where the node size indicates how often works like Albino et al. (2015) and Meijer and Bolfvar (2016) have been referenced. Two articles stand as significant theoretical bases within this research domain. Dense node connections demonstrate the strong correlation between these works which is shown through Silva et al. (2018) and Appio et al. (2019) located in the red cluster.

In addition, the color coding within the figure delineates various clusters of research topics. The green cluster predominantly concerns the definitions and management framework of smart cities. The seminal works (such as Albino et al. (2015)) highlight the multidimensional attributes of smart cities. The red cluster is centered on the integration of smart city technological applications with sustainable solutions, exemplified by Silva et al. (2018), who discuss the enhancements of energy efficiency and urban resilience through smart cities. Meanwhile, the blue cluster mainly revolves around the interplay between policy and technology, with Ruhlandt (2018) investigating the impact of smart governance on urban sustainable development.

4.2. TBL theory and content analysis

4.2.1. TBL theory

The TBL concept was introduced by Elkington (1994) to achieve sustainable development. It encourages organizations to consider and balance the three bottom lines of (i) economic, (ii) society, and (iii) environmental prosperity in their decision-making processes (as shown

Fig. 3. Co-Citation Network Visualization.

in Fig. 4). While initially conceptualized for organizations, TBL has been widely applied to urban sustainability. For example, Yigitcanlar et al. (2023) explore City 4.0 through a triple bottom line approach, emphasizing technology-driven urban sustainability, while Margherita et al. (2023) emphasized its relevance in assessing urban frameworks.

4.2.2. Dimension and analysis of sustainability in a smart city

Six dimensions of smart city sustainability are indicated as the basis for this study, which are adapted from Hoang and Nguyen (2021) and Kozłowski and Suwar (2021). These dimensions are not only theoretical constructs but reflect how cities globally are implementing practical measures to attain sustainability objectives. For example, technologies like IoT-based air quality monitoring systems are used to reduce pollution and improve public health (Ullo and Sinha, 2020) in the “Smart Environment” dimension. Similarly, in the “Smart Mobility” dimension, cities are adopting electric vehicles, bike-sharing schemes, and real-time public transportation management to promote sustainable urban mobility and to decrease reliance on fossil fuels (Brzeziński, 2024).

Several keywords were assigned to the six dimensions, reflecting the practical ways in which smart city technologies contribute to sustainability in the 82 articles that were examined. The following section summarises the assigned keywords and the dimension that it corresponds to in the paper, illustrating how the social, environmental and economic sustainable-development goals are integrated through technological innovation in smart cities.

(1) Smart People

The “smart people” strategy, within the TBL model, promotes sustainable development by focusing on education, talent cultivation, and social inclusion. The purpose of this strategy is to revolutionize how individuals interact with the public and private sectors by creating digital equality through education, enabling more effective service delivery via new technologies (Intille, 2006). A prime example is Singapore’s Smart Nation Initiative, which enhances human capital by offering career options, job opportunities, and vocational training (Hoe, 2016).

(2) Smart Governance

Integrating the conceptual framework into smart government helps build sustainable governance by strengthening connections between decision-makers, residents, businesses, and institutions (Pojani and Stead, 2015). Smart government can help to ensure that policies and projects are beneficial to all stakeholders and increase long-term

Fig. 4. Triple Bottom Line.

sustainability in economic, social, and environmental terms. Tokyo exemplifies this approach with its electronic medical record system and campus information service, which enhances communication and decision-making, improving resilience and stakeholder engagement (Sarker et al., 2021).

(3) Smart Environment

Integrating the TBL framework into smart government helps build sustainable governance by strengthening connections between decision-makers, residents, businesses, and institutions (Poiani and Stead, 2015). Additionally, building area plays a significant role in influencing energy consumption and, consequently, the environmental sustainability of urban systems. Cho et al. (2021) demonstrate that integrating energy-efficient designs into large buildings within smart city projects can significantly reduce energy demands. An Illinois law (Climate and Equitable Jobs Act (CEJA), passed in 2021) shows how legislation can drive a green transformation and the integration of renewable energy (Rozhkov, 2023). Smart environment policies are an important part of addressing unsustainable urban growth and its environmental impact (Aletà et al., 2017). By focusing on renewable energy, these policies enhance city livability and sustainability for both citizens and visitors.

(4) Smart Living

Smart living fits very well with the sustainability elements if its work-leisure balance is applied to a technologically enhanced environment, and it promotes efficient resource use and personal comfort (Bier et al., 2018). Hong Kong’s 2017 smart city programme follows these principles by concentrating on smart government and smart economy (Hong Kong Special Administrative Region Government, 2020), and implementing technological solutions to enhance the living standard by enhancing resource productivity and optimizing living conditions (Anthopoulos, 2017) in a sustainable, inclusive and personal wellbeing-friendly way. Smart living as a sustainable way of life contributes to a prosperous economy, a socially inclusive society and environmental stewardship.

(5) Smart Economy

The smart economy, oriented towards resource efficiency and driving economic vitality through innovation, is a key focus for smart

cities as they strive to maintain economic competitiveness through technological innovation (Kumar and Dahiya, 2017). Shanghai has modernized its industrial mix and boosted emerging industries by improving labor force skills and leveraging big data and AI (Yu et al., 2019). Furthermore, building upon big data, artificial intelligence, and the Internet of Things, Shanghai is overcoming challenges in urban development, government efficiency, and performance. It is also improving the living standards of its citizens. Meanwhile, workforce skills also play a key role in economic sustainability. Kumar and Kumar and Dahiya (2017) and Yu et al. (2019) show that improving workforce skills directly contributes to productivity, innovation, and industry diversification. And these items are key drivers of economic dynamism. In the context of smart cities in particular, a skilled workforce contributes to economic resilience and competitiveness.

(6) Smart Mobility

Smart mobility offers easy access to local and global transport systems (including the availability and safety of mobility) as a result of technological advancements in technologies (Aletà et al., 2017). Specifically, smart mobility emphasizes enhancing the efficiency and service quality of urban transportation to improve the utilization and adoption of new mobility solutions. It also increasing the mobility of individuals via effective mobility management and strategic infrastructure allocation (Papa and Lauwers, 2015). A successful “smart mobility” strategy aligns with the TBL model by striking a balance between the needs of the present and the imperatives of a sustainable future.

4.3. Conceptual framework

Using the TBL, a conceptual framework for evaluating the level of sustainability in smart cities is proposed in Fig. 5 from multiple dimensions, and the details of the influencing factors are presented in Table 2. This framework includes (a) urban governance, (b) energy performance, and (c) economic structures.

Urban governance transcends traditional administrative duties by

Fig. 5. Conceptual Framework for Assessing the Sustainability of a Smart City.

Table 2
Influencing Factors Based on Three Parameters: Social, Environmental, and Economics.

Perspectives	Parameters	Factors	References
Social	Urban Governance	Equity	(Toli and Murtagh, 2020)
		Gratification of fundamental human needs	
		Community autonomy	(Meijer and Bolivar, 2016)
		Citizen well-being	
Environmental	Energy Performance	Good policy	(Ben-Eli, 2018) (Cho et al., 2021) (Cong et al., 2016) (Kristl et al., 2020) (Lu et al., 2019) (Toli and Murtagh, 2020)
		Innovate decision-making	
		Citizen participation	
		Energy consumption	
		Building area	
		Building structure	
		Age of the building	
Economic	Economic Structure	Type of the building	(Wang et al., 2019) (Nebiker et al., 2021) (Zhuang et al., 2020) (Yigitcanlar et al., 2019)
		Conservation of the natural environment	
		Natural resources	
		Energy production-based economy	
		Industry mix	
		Labor force skills	
		Government regulation	
		Economic vitality	

ensuring that equity and the meeting of fundamental human needs are prioritized as vital elements of sustainability. This governance model is driven by innovative decision-making and uses citizen participation platforms to create transparency and foster community autonomy (Bastos et al., 2022). The role of governance is to promote citizen well-being as smart cities evolve. This is critical for maintaining a stable and prosperous society. Furthermore, through the implementation of effective policies that correspond with the conservation of the natural resources and social equity, urban governance functions as the core of sustainable development (van der Jagt et al., 2021).

Smart cities could be intelligently powered by technologies such as smart grids that enable real-time electricity-usage monitoring and that support the control and self-optimization of building sensors. Together, these promote low-energy usage in residential and commercial areas. Energy efficiency also depends on the size of buildings, floor area, and building age. Therefore, energy planning must be incorporated into urban development in the future (Chalal et al., 2016). Conservation of natural resources is important, leading policymakers to focus on minimizing the environmental harm of smart cities. Moreover, smart cities cultivate focus on building energy management systems for controlling the usage of consumption and energy efficiency (Gharaibeh et al., 2017). This leads to healthier, sustainable, and energy efficient environments for urban communities and helps to fulfill the goals of sustainable development over time.

A resilient structure is a prerequisite for the sustainability of smart cities (Xiong et al., 2022). Cities can protect themselves from economic shocks and ensure economic vitality by promoting a diversified industry mix and developing labor force skills. Government regulations play a leading role in balancing this, by guiding the development of industry and making sure that environmental and economic policies are coordinated. The development of a knowledge-based economy supports the growth of green industries and innovation and this dynamic relationship between industry and education fosters a partnership that drives economic development while safeguarding natural resources (Wang et al., 2023).

This conceptual framework realises sustainable development in smart cities by the cooperation between three sectors: urban governance, energy performance, and economic structure. The development of smart cities is mainly supported by the sector of urban governance. Urban governance is the foundation of smart city development, providing a community of social equity, justice and openness, and a system of rules and regulations to coordinate the orderly operation of other sectors (David et al., 2018). Energy performance is the key to the approach, which optimises resource utilization through improved energy efficiency, and exerts a direct influence on environmental conditions. Economic structure is the pillar for the long-term development which promote a sustainable growth through the development of industrial structure diversification and innovation. These three sectors are interrelated and a feedback loop is formed, in which the improvement of energy efficiency and economic growth enhance governance and technological investment, which will result in an amplification of the effect to ensure the sustainable and adaptable development of cities.

5. Conclusions

Smart cities and sustainability have emerged as fascinating interconnected fields of study over the last decade. A holistic understanding of the connection between sustainability and smart cities has important managerial implications for future city developments. The integration of smart cities and sustainability has not been fully investigated and the purpose of this systematic literature review was to fill this research gap. This study examined 82 articles selected from more than 2500 publications. Network visualization illustrates the strong correlation between sustainability and smart cities, highlighting their interconnectedness and the multifaceted factors affecting sustainability. Furthermore, this study also delved into the TBL theory, emphasizing its applicability in the development of smart cities to achieve a balance between economic, social, and environmental imperatives. Building on prior studies on the six dimensions of smart cities, a conceptual framework for evaluating the level of sustainability in smart cities was proposed.

Nevertheless, there are still several limitations in this study. First, the range of time in this literature research and analysis was focused on the past five years and failed to cover research results over a longer time span. Secondly, this study only focused on a limited number of literature sources, and future studies could be expanded in terms of data volume and research scope. The quantitative assessment of smart city sustainability requires more empirical research for verification.

This study has important theoretical implications and practical significance for the future development of smart cities. The conceptual framework and analysis proposed in this study can serve as a reference for promoting and qualifying the sustainability of smart cities from a theoretical perspective for policy makers and urban planners. In practice, the integration of technological innovation, policies and regulations, energy and environment, citizen participation, economic models, and financing mechanisms will become important factors affecting the sustainability of smart cities.

Future research should focus on a several key areas. First, longitudinal studies are needed to understand the long-term impact of smart city projects on sustainability. Second, researchers should utilize expansive datasets and real-world case studies to validate and refine the proposed framework. Third, integrating knowledge from diverse fields such as technology, urban planning, and social sciences, will be crucial in addressing the complex challenges encountered by smart cities. Lastly, examining the specific roles of governance, innovation, and citizen participation will clarify the pathway for cities to achieve sustainable development.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Qinhan Gu: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation.

Michael C.P. Sing: Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Marcus Jefferies:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Sittimont Kanjanabootra:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

References

- Aelenei, L., Ferreira, A., Monteiro, C. S., Gomes, R., Gonçalves, H., Camelo, S., & Silva, C. (2016). Smart city: A systematic approach towards a sustainable urban transformation. *Energy Procedia*, 91, 970–979.
- Ahvenniemi, H., Huovila, A., Pinto-Seppä, I., & Airaksinen, M. (2017). What are the differences between sustainable and smart cities? *Cities*, 60, 234–245.
- Aina, Y. A. (2017). Achieving smart sustainable cities with GeoICT support: The Saudi evolving smart cities. *Cities*, 71, 49–58.
- Albino, V., Berardi, U., & Dangelico, R. M. (2015). Smart cities: Definitions, dimensions, performance, and initiatives. *J. Urban Technol.*, 22(1), 3–21.
- Aletà, N. B., Alonso, C. M., & Ruiz, R. M. A. (2017). Smart mobility and smart environment in the Spanish cities. *Transportation research procedia*, 24, 163–170.
- Allam, Z., & Newman, P. (2018). Redefining the smart city: Culture, metabolism and governance. *Smart Cities*, 1(1), 4–25.
- Anthopoulos, L. G. (2017). The smart city in practice. In *Understanding Smart Cities: A Tool for Smart Government or an Industrial Trick?* (pp. 47–185). Springer.
- Appio, F. P., Lima, M., & Paroutis, S. (2019). Understanding Smart Cities: Innovation ecosystems, technological advancements, and societal challenges. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.*, 142, 1–14.
- Bakuc, T., Almirall, E., & Wareham, J. (2013). A smart city initiative: the case of Barcelona. *J. Knowl. Econ.*, 4(2), 135–148.
- Bastos, D., Fernández-Caballero, A., Pereira, A., & Rocha, N. P. (2022). Smart city applications to promote citizen participation in city management and governance: A systematic review. *Informatics*.
- Ben-Eli, M. U. (2018). Sustainability: definition and five core principles, a systems perspective. *Sustain. Sci.*, 13(5), 1337–1343.
- Bhati, A., Hansen, M., & Chan, C. M. (2017). Energy conservation through smart homes in a smart city: A lesson for Singapore households. *Energy Policy*, 104, 230–239.
- Bibri, S. E. (2019). On the sustainability of smart and smarter cities in the era of big data: an interdisciplinary and transdisciplinary literature review. *J. Big Data*, 6(1), 1–64.
- Bibri, S. E. (2021). Data-driven smart eco-cities and sustainable integrated districts: A best-evidence synthesis approach to an extensive literature review. *Eur. J. Futures Res.*, 9(1), 1–43. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40309-021-00181-4>
- Bibri, S. E., & Krogstie, J. (2017). Smart sustainable cities of the future: An extensive interdisciplinary literature review. *Sustain. Cities Soc.*, 31, 183–212.
- Bibri, S. E., & Krogstie, J. (2020). Environmentally data-driven smart sustainable cities: Applied innovative solutions for energy efficiency, pollution reduction, and urban metabolism. *Energy Inform.*, 3(1), 29.
- Bier, N., Paquette, G., & Macoir, J. (2018). Smartphone for smart living: Using new technologies to cope with everyday limitations in semantic dementia. *Neuropsychol. Rehabil.*, 28(5), 734–754.
- Bifulco, F., Tregua, M., Amitrano, C. C., & D'Auria, A. (2016). ICT and sustainability in smart cities management. *Int. J. Public Sect. Manag.*, 29(2), 132–147.
- Brzeziński, L. (2024). Social Aspects of Smart Urban Mobility. *Encyclopedia*, 4(2), 864–873.
- Caragliu, A., & Del Bo, C. F. (2019). Smart innovative cities: The impact of Smart City policies on urban innovation. *Technological Forecasting and Social Change*, 142, 373–383.
- Chalal, M. L., Benachir, M., White, M., & Shrahily, R. (2016). Energy planning and forecasting approaches for improving physical improvement strategies in the building sector: A review. *Renew. Sust. Energ. Rev.*, 64, 761–776.
- Cho, K., Yang, J., Kim, T., & Jang, W. (2021). Influence of building characteristics and renovation techniques on the energy-saving performances of EU smart city projects. *Energy and Buildings*, 252, Article 111477.
- Cong, X., Liu, Z., & Wang, Y. (2016). Building smart cities in China: problems and countermeasures. *Chin. J. Urban Environ. Stud.*, 4(03), 1650022.
- da Silva Tomadon, L., & do Couto, E. V., de Vries, W. T., & Moretto, Y. (2024). Smart city and sustainability indicators: a bibliometric literature review. *Discov. Sustain.*, 5(1), 143.
- Daptardar, V., & Gore, M. (2019). Smart cities for sustainable development in India: opportunities and challenges. *European Journal of Sustainable Development*, 8(3), 133.
- David, N., McNutt, J. G., & Justice, J. B. (2018). *Smart cities, transparency, civic technology and reinventing government* (pp. 19–34). Smart Technologies for Smart Governments: Transparency, Efficiency and Organizational Issues.
- De Guimarães, J. C. F., Severo, E. A., Júnior, L. A. F., Da Costa, W. P. L. B., & Salmoria, F. T. (2020). Governance and quality of life in smart cities: Towards sustainable development goals. *J. Clean. Prod.*, 253, Article 119926.
- Dincă, G., Milan, A.-A., Andronic, M. L., Pasztori, A.-M., & Dincă, D. (2022). Does Circular Economy Contribute to Smart Cities' Sustainable Development? *Int. J. Environ. Res. Public Health*, 19(13), 7627. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ijerph19137627>
- Dubé, L., & Paré, G. (2003). Rigor in information systems positivist case research: current practices, trends, and recommendations. *MIS Q.*, 597–636.
- Elkington, J. (1994). Towards the sustainable corporation: Win-win-win business strategies for sustainable development. *Calif. Manag. Rev.*, 36(2), 90–100.
- Elkington, J. (2013). Enter the triple bottom line. In *The triple bottom line: Does it all add up?* (pp. 1–16). Routledge.
- Evans, J., Karvonen, A., Luque-Ayala, A., Martin, C., McCormick, K., Raven, R., & Palgan, Y. V. (2019). Smart and sustainable cities? Pipereams, practicalities and possibilities. In , 24. In (pp. 557–564). Taylor & Francis.
- Foo, Y. Z., O'Dea, R. E., Koricheva, J., Nakagawa, S., & Lagisz, M. (2021). A practical guide to question formation, systematic searching and study screening for literature reviews in ecology and evolution. *Methods Ecol. Evol.*, 12(9), 1705–1720.
- Garau, C., & Pavan, V. M. (2018). Evaluating urban quality: Indicators and assessment tools for smart sustainable cities. *Sustainability*, 10(3), 575.
- Gharaibeh, A., Salahuddin, M. A., Hussini, S. J., Khreishah, A., Khalil, I., Guizani, M., & Al-Fuqaha, A. (2017). Smart cities: A survey on data management, security, and enabling technologies. *IEEE Communications Surveys & Tutorials*, 19(4), 2456–2501.
- Goyal, L. K., Chauhan, R., Kumar, R., & Rai, H. S. (2020). Use of BIM in Development of Smart Cities: A Review. In *IOP Conference Series. Materials Science and Engineering*.
- Haarstad, H., & Wathne, M. W. (2019). Are smart city projects catalyzing urban energy sustainability? *Energy Policy*, 129, 918–925.
- Hoang, A. T., & Nguyen, X. P. (2021). Integrating renewable sources into energy system for smart city as a sagacious strategy towards clean and sustainable process. *J. Clean. Prod.*, 305, Article 127161.
- Hoe, S. L. (2016). Defining a smart nation: the case of Singapore. *J. Inf. Commun. Ethics Soc.*, 14(4), 323–333.
- Hong Kong Special Administrative Region Government. (2020). *Hong Kong smart city blueprint 2.0*. Innovation and Technology Bureau. https://www.smartcity.gov.hk/modules/custom/custom_global_js_css/assets/files/HKSmartCityBlueprint%282CH%29v2.pdf.
- Intille, S. S. (2006). The goal: smart people, not smart homes. In *Proceedings of ICOST2006: The International Conference on Smart Homes and Health Telematics*. Amsterdam: IOS Press.
- Ivars-Baidal, J. A., Vera-Rebollo, J. F., Perles-Ribes, J., Femenia-Serra, F., & Celdrán-Bernabeu, M. A. (2023). Sustainable tourism indicators: what's new within the smart city/destination approach? *J. Sustain. Tour.*, 31(7), 1556–1582.
- Kashef, M., Visvizi, A., & Troisi, O. (2021). Smart city as a smart service system: Human-computer interaction and smart city surveillance systems. *Comput. Hum. Behav.*, 124, Article 106923. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.chb.2021.106923>
- Kong, X., Zhao, X., Wang, C., Duan, Q., Sha, G., & Liu, L. (2022). Promote the international development of Energy Internet technology standards based on key competition mode. *Sustain. Cities Soc.*, 86, Article 104151.
- Kozłowski, W., & Suwar, K. (2021). *Smart city: definitions, dimensions, and initiatives*.
- Kristl, Ž., Temeljotov Salaj, A., & Roumboutsos, A. (2020). Sustainability and universal design aspects in heritage building refurbishment. *Facilities*, 38(9/10), 599–623.
- Kuhlman, T., & Farrington, J. (2010). What is sustainability? *Sustainability*, 2(11), 3436–3448.
- Kumar, V., & Dahiya, B. (2017). Smart economy in smart cities. In *Smart economy in smart cities* (pp. 3–76). Springer.
- Laila, N. (2021). Energy economics in Islamic countries: A bibliometric review. *Int. J. Energy Econ. Policy*, 11(2), 88–95.
- Liu, R., Dong, X., Wang, X.-c., Zhang, P., Liu, M., & Zhang, Y. (2021). Study on the relationship among the urbanization process, ecosystem services and human well-being in an arid region in the context of carbon flow: Taking the Manas river basin as an example. *Ecol. Indic.*, 132, 108248.
- Lu, H.-P., Chen, C.-S., & Yu, H. (2019). Technology roadmap for building a smart city: An exploring study on methodology. *Futur. Gener. Comput. Syst.*, 97, 727–742.
- Margherita, E. G., Escobar, S. D., Esposito, G., & Crutzen, N. (2023). Exploring the potential impact of smart urban technologies on urban sustainability using structural topic modelling: Evidence from Belgium. *Cities*, 141, Article 104475.
- Meijer, A., & Bolívar, M. P. R. (2016). Governing the smart city: a review of the literature on smart urban governance. *Int. Rev. Adm. Sci.*, 82(2), 392–408.
- Moldan, B., Janoušková, S., & Hák, T. (2012). How to understand and measure environmental sustainability: Indicators and targets. *Ecol. Indic.*, 17, 4–13.
- Morgan, L. H. (2019). *Ancient society: Or, researches in the lines of human progress from savagery, through barbarism to civilization*. Good Press.
- Moynihan, R., Sanders, S., Michaleff, Z. A., Scott, A. M., Clark, J., To, To, E. J., Jones, M., Kitchener, E., Fox, M., & Johansson, M. (2021). Impact of COVID-19 pandemic on utilisation of healthcare services: a systematic review. *BMJ Open*, 11(3), e045343.

- Nebiker, S., Meyer, J., Blaser, S., Ammann, M., & Rhyner, S. (2021). Outdoor mobile mapping and AI-based 3D object detection with low-cost RGB-D cameras: The use case of on-street parking statistics. *Remote Sens.*, *13*(16), 3099.
- Papa, E., & Lauwers, D. (2015). Smart mobility: Opportunity or threat to innovate places and cities. 20th international conference on urban planning and regional development in the information society (REAL CORP 2015).
- Pojani, D., & Stead, D. (2015). Sustainable urban transport in the developing world: beyond megacities. *Sustainability*, *7*(6), 7784–7805.
- Ramirez Lopez, L. J., & Grijalba Castro, A. I. (2020). Sustainability and resilience in smart city planning: A review. *Sustainability*, *13*(1), 181.
- Ribes, J. F. P., & Baidal, J. I. (2018). Smart sustainability: A new perspective in the sustainable tourism debate. *Investigaciones Regionales-Journal of Regional Research* (42), 151–170.
- Ritchie, H., & Roser, M. (2018). *Urbanization. Our world in data.*
- Rozhkov, A. (2023). Harnessing European policies for energy planning in Illinois: Overcoming barriers and transitioning to a climate-neutral society. *Sustain. Cities Soc.*, *98*, Article 104803.
- Ruhlandt, R. W. S. (2018). The governance of smart cities: A systematic literature review. *Cities*, *81*, 1–23.
- Sarker, S., Jamal, L., Ahmed, S. F., & Irtisam, N. (2021). Robotics and artificial intelligence in healthcare during COVID-19 pandemic: A systematic review. *Robot. Auton. Syst.*, *146*, Article 103902.
- Seuwou, P., Banissi, E., & Ubakanma, G. (2020). The future of mobility with connected and autonomous vehicles in smart cities. In *Digital twin technologies and smart cities* (pp. 37–52). Springer.
- Silva, B. N., Khan, M., & Han, K. (2018). Towards sustainable smart cities: A review of trends, architectures, components, and open challenges in smart cities. *Sustain. Cities Soc.*, *38*, 697–713.
- Tariq, M. U. (2024). Smart Transportation Systems: Paving the Way for Sustainable Urban Mobility. In *Contemporary Solutions for Sustainable Transportation Practices* (pp. 254–283). IGI Global.
- Toli, A. M., & Murtagh, N. (2020). The concept of sustainability in smart city definitions. *Frontiers in Built Environment*, *6*, 77.
- Trindade, E. P., Hinnig, M. P. F., Moreira da Costa, E., Marques, J. S., Bastos, R. C., & Yigitcanlar, T. (2017). Sustainable development of smart cities: A systematic review of the literature. *J. Open Innov.: Technol. Mark. Complex.*, *3*(3), 11.
- Ullo, S. L., & Sinha, G. R. (2020). Advances in smart environment monitoring systems using IoT and sensors. *Sensors*, *20*(11), 3113.
- Umar, M., Ji, X., Kirikkaleli, D., Shahbaz, M., & Zhou, X. (2020). Environmental cost of natural resources utilization and economic growth: can China shift some burden through globalization for sustainable development? *Sustainable Development*, *28*(6), 1678–1688.
- van der Jagt, A. P., Kiss, B., Hirose, S., & Takahashi, W. (2021). Nature-based solutions or debacles? The politics of reflexive governance for sustainable and just cities. *Frontiers in Sustainable Cities*, *2*, Article 583833.
- Vanli, T. (2024). Ranking of global smart cities using dynamic factor analysis. *Soc. Indic. Res.*, *171*(2), 405–437.
- Visvizi, A., Lytras, M. D., Damiani, E., & Mathkour, H. (2018). Policy making for smart cities: Innovation and social inclusive economic growth for sustainability. *Journal of Science and Technology Policy Management*, *9*(2), 126–133.
- Wang, M., & Debbage, N. (2021). Urban morphology and traffic congestion: Longitudinal evidence from US cities. *Comput. Environ. Urban. Syst.*, *89*, Article 101676.
- Wang, Y., Ren, H., Dong, L., Park, H.-S., Zhang, Y., & Xu, Y. (2019). Smart solutions shape for sustainable low-carbon future: A review on smart cities and industrial parks in China. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.*, *144*, 103–117.
- Wang, Y.-Z., Wu, C.-C., & Wang, X.-Q. (2021). Bibliometric study of pain after spinal cord injury. *Neural Plasticity*, *2021*, 1–15.
- Wang, Z., Huang, Y., Ankras, V., & Dai, J. (2023). Greening the knowledge-based economies: Harnessing natural resources and innovation in information and communication technologies for green growth. *Res. Policy*, *86*, Article 104181.
- Wilkinson, K. P. (1991). *The community in rural America.*
- Xiong, K., Sharifi, A., & He, B.-J. (2022). Resilient-smart cities: theoretical insights. In *Resilient smart cities: Theoretical and empirical insights* (pp. 93–118). Springer.
- Yaxue, Q. (2020). Convolutional Neural Networks for Literature Retrieval. In *2020 International Conference on Computer Vision. Image and: Deep Learning (CVIDL).*
- Ye, B. H., Ye, H., & Law, R. (2020). Systematic review of smart tourism research. *Sustainability*, *12*(8), 3401.
- Yigitcanlar, T., Han, H., Kamruzzaman, M., Ioppolo, G., & Sabatini-Marques, J. (2019). The making of smart cities: Are Songdo, Masdar, Amsterdam, San Francisco and Brisbane the best we could build? *Land Use Policy*, *88*, Article 104187.
- Yigitcanlar, T., Velibeyoglu, K., & Martinez-Fernandez, C. (2008). Rising knowledge cities: the role of urban knowledge precincts. *J. Knowl. Manag.*, *12*(5), 8–20. <https://doi.org/10.1108/13673270810902902>
- Yigitcanlar, T., Xia, B., Cortese, T. T. P., & Sabatini-Marques, J. (2023). Understanding City 4.0: A Triple Bottom Line Approach. *Sustainability*, *16*(1), 326.
- Yu, J., Wen, Y., Jin, J., & Zhang, Y. (2019). Towards a service-dominant platform for public value co-creation in a smart city: Evidence from two metropolitan cities in China. *Technol. Forecast. Soc. Chang.*, *142*, 168–182.
- Zhou, J., Yu, L., & Choguill, C. L. (2021). Co-evolution of technology and rural society: The blossoming of taobao villages in the information era, China. *J. Rural. Stud.*, *83*, 81–87.
- Zhuang, H., Zhang, J., & CB, S., & Muthu, B. A.. (2020). Sustainable smart city building construction methods. *Sustainability*, *12*(12), 4947.